

CHILD PERSONALITY DEVELOPMENT AND MORAL EDUCATION

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Abstract. *The article discusses the issues of child personality development and the importance of combining it with moral and aesthetic education. It also touches upon the completion of the process of mastering the speech of children in the age of preschool age, the impact of speech and communication on the child in the development of mental processes, the opportunities that arise in him with the help of speech, and the organization of integrated training in preschool educational organizations. Raised*

Keywords: *education, parents, children, moral-aesthetic qualities, spirituality, pre-school age, development, speech, communication, 5-6 years old.*

The scope of the reforms carried out in our society, in the age of developing science and technology, parents should provide their children with the necessary education and upbringing based on today's requirements, taking into account their age-appropriate and unique characteristics. They are increasingly aware of the need to grow up as a high, mature person in all respects.

A person with an independent point of view and high spirituality is distinguished from others by his moral and aesthetic qualities. He doesn't see the bad behavior he doesn't deserve on others. Moral science discusses complex conflicts and problems between evil and goodness. Moral-aesthetic feelings are experienced in the process of activity and behavior. It reflects and expresses the child's attitude to the various things that happen in his life, whether they are wonderful or absurd, tragic or funny, noble or disgusting, sophisticated or ugly.

Pedagogical scientists insist that a child cannot become a well-rounded ideologically-politically developed person without full moral-aesthetic education. At its heart lies the issue of harmonious development of the human personality in all aspects by educating and improving feelings, imagination and thoughts about the beauty of the world.

The formation of children's moral and aesthetic qualities requires clarification of new pedagogical tools for organizing the preschool education process. The problem of forming moral and aesthetic qualities as a basis for the development of the personality of a preschool-aged child is first of all clearly defined by our Government: to instill in children the feeling of love for the Motherland, respect for the family, the national, historical and cultural values of their people, the environment forming a careful attitude to the environment; forming the child's personality, developing his creative abilities, ensuring that he gains social experience (Approved by Appendix 1 of the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. 391 of May 13, 2019 "General-type State and Non-State Preschool Educational Organizations" on Regulation¹. Also, in the curriculum of the preschool education organization "First Step" approved by the decision of the

¹Ўзбекистон Республикаси Вазирлар Маҳкамасининг 2019 йил 13 майдаги “Мақтабгача таълим ташкилотлари фаолиятини янада такомиллаштириш тўғрисида”ги 391-сон [Қарори](#).

board meeting No. 4 of the Ministry of Preschool Education of the Republic of Uzbekistan on July 7, 2018, "Education of preschool children Competency approach is related to preparing a growing child's personality for life, mastering moral norms and values, communicating with other people, and building the image of "I". to prepare for the formation of methods of activity² specified. In particular, after the completion of the educational activity in the field of "Creativity", it is shown that a 6-7-year-old child will have the following abilities: shows interest in art and culture; appreciates national traditions and perceives them as a part of everyday life; independently expresses his preference for a certain type of art; uses acquired knowledge and skills to create and implement creative plans in various life situations; understands the role of human creativity in changing the world³.

Ethical-aesthetic qualities are the issue of raising children's knowledge about beauty, the reality of life, objects, their variety and types, self-control, openness to communication, distinguishing between good and bad, and self-evaluation. includes.

In preschool pedagogy and psychology, 5-6 years are accepted as the age period before high school. As a rule, the process of acquiring speech as a complex and long-lasting process ends in the pre-school age. Language becomes a tool for thinking and communication, an object of conscious learning. Because during the preparation of the child for school, teaching to read and write begins, and phonemic development is completed. At this age, the vocabulary of speech increases rapidly, and its grammatical construction develops. Also, children learn syntactic (sentence formation) and morphological (word formation) rules. As noted by M.I.Lesina, communication turns from a situational description into an object of the cognitive process. Children begin to pay special attention to the uniqueness of interpersonal relationships⁴.

At preschool age, perception loses its initial affective description: emotional and perceptual processes are differentiated, conscious perception is formed, oriented to analysis, to a specific goal. The child shows the ability to actively use free actions - searching, paying attention, observing, naming various objects and the state, signs and qualities of relationships between them using speech. The development of thinking goes from visual-active to visual-imagery, and then to verbal thinking. That is why visual-imagery, in accordance with V.V.Lavrentev's words, representational intelligence, thinking based on imagination is considered the main⁵.

According to the well-known pedagogic scientist P.Ya.Galperin, three areas of development develop at the end of the preschool period:

- a) formation of free behavior based on compliance with rules;
- b) mastering the means and norms of cognitive activity;
- c) orientation from self-centered thinking⁶.

Significant changes occur in children's thinking during the preschool age: their worldview expands, thinking operations improve, new knowledge and skills appear, and therefore speech develops actively. Only mental and language skills are acquired in the process of communication

²"Ilk qadam" maktabgacha ta'lim muassasasining o'quv dasturi. – Toshkent, 2018. 9-bet.

³"Ilk qadam" maktabgacha ta'lim muassasasining o'quv dasturi. – Toshkent, 2018. 12-bet.

⁴Немов, Р. С. Психология [Текст] : учеб. для студентов высш. пед. учеб. заведений : в 3 кн. / Р. С. Немов. – М. : ВЛАДОС, 2011. – Кн. 2 : Психология образования. – 608 с. – С.45.

⁵Лаврентьев В. В. Значение игры в работе с детьми // Начальная школа. – 1999. –№ 5. – С. 84-87.

⁶Коршунова, Л. С. Воображение и рациональность [Текст] : опыт методолог. анализа познават. функции воображения / Л. С. Коршунова, Б. И. Пружинин. – М. : Изд-во МГУ, 1999. – 278 с. – С.108.

with the environment. As the child grows, the structure of communication becomes more complex, which, in turn, requires mastering complex forms of speech.

Many changes occur in the cognitive processes in preschool age. According to V.S.Mukhina, perception changes from affective to emotional and perceptive at the age of 6-7⁷. Perception becomes analytical, goal-oriented and conscious. It shows free actions - searching, checking, observing. At the age of 6-7, the development of voluntary attention is of high importance. Through this, there is an opportunity to improve the planned speech function. According to V.S.Mukhina, this reflects a universal method of concentration. Thanks to speech, there is an opportunity to verbally express the specific tasks of objects, as well as to focus on the next activity⁸. For the preschool education system, the problem of children's cognitive activity is very important for this age period. Rational consideration of the constantly growing amount of knowledge places new demands on the education of the growing generation. First of all, there is the task of developing cognitive activity.

The high level of thinking and feeling of children of this age causes them to grieve together and belong to the happenings. Therefore, it is necessary to arouse interest in environmental phenomena and people's actions in children from early childhood and to form an emotional and positive attitude towards them. Children of preschool age are characterized by vigorous development. During the preschool period, strong changes occur in connection with various directions, the main types of activities, as well as mental processes, actively develop. For example, a child's memory changes both qualitatively and quantitatively. For example, children of the senior group remember about 7-8 objects before school, and 10-12 objects in the preparatory groups. Qualitative changes are that preschool children remember not only interesting information for him, but also recommended memorization accepts tasks, can use special methods of remembering necessary information⁹.

A child remembers things that evoke an interesting and positive image for him. Psychologists say that the volume of the described materials determines the emotional response to objects and events. According to V.S.Mukhina, a high state of attention determines orientation to the environment and an emotional reaction to it. Also, the originality of the content of the external imagination ensures that attention is high in connection with age¹⁰.

Imagination is one of the most important changes in preschool age. At this stage, qualities such as originality and discretion are formed. At the age of 5-6, children can independently weave small fairy tales based on the sequence of events on the proposed topics. At the age of seven, children are able to base their imaginations on a specific direction and to make partial changes to it according to a pre-determined step-by-step plan. Preschool children learn many ways of behavior and behavior in a short period of time. They carefully observe the behavior of those around them. They imitate the behavior, attitude, self-control, speech and behavior of adults. As a result, they begin to feel the need to communicate with their peers. In this process, the instructions and examples of adults, especially parents and educators, play an important role.

The activities of family members and educators are of particular importance in the formation of high moral and aesthetic qualities in the minds of their students. After all, if there are such qualities as honesty, politeness, modesty, mutual respect, in a word, sincere relationship

⁷Мухина В.С. Детская психология. – М.: Апрель-Пресс :ЭКСМО-Пресс, 2000. – 352 с. – С.88.

⁸Мухина В.С. Детская психология. – М.: Апрель-Пресс :ЭКСМО-Пресс, 2000. – 352 с. – С.37.

⁹Кряжева Н.Л. Развитие эмоционального мира детей – Екатеринбург: У-Фактория, 2004. – 192 с. – С.6.

¹⁰Мухина В.С. Детская психология. – М.: Апрель-Пресс :ЭКСМО-Пресс, 2000. – 352 с. – С.32.

between the family members, the educator and the child, then these exemplary moral-aesthetic qualities have a positive effect on children. The child draws correct conclusions from the actions he sees in his family and around him, strives to respect his loved ones and fulfill his duty conscientiously. Artistic and aesthetic development is carried out at all ages. However, the earlier the goal-oriented artistic-aesthetic effect is implemented, the more effective it will be. From the early development age, through play activities, the child seeks to know the environment, through imitation, he acquires the elements of cooperative activity and communication culture together with people. The game is the main and very effective way to awaken creative potential, develop imagination and form the first aesthetic impressions. Skills acquired in the process of communication and activity form an elementary aesthetic attitude to reality and art in a preschool child¹¹.

Taking into account the peculiarities of preschool children, it is necessary to take into account the principle of integration in their artistic and aesthetic development:

- the behavior and activity of a preschool child reflects "insufficiently stratified wholeness";
- early understanding of the components of integrity provides an individual with the opportunity to "quickly and integrally see the uniqueness of things and events";
- early acquisition of knowledge about the holistic view of the world enriches the child's theoretical concepts, creates favorable conditions for enriching integral images at the level of re-perception of reality¹².

In the modern practice of pre-school education, the organization and conduct of integrated classes has already become widely popular. The methodology of organizing integrated classes has been developed and is widely used in preschool education organizations in our republic. Training in all development centers (building and construction, plot-role games and dramatization, language and speech, science and nature, art and music, music and rhythm) is part of the educational activities of preschool children. recorded as the main form. However, the integration of various types of children's activities was not fully taken into account in the organization of the process of mastering preschool education programs.

As a conclusion to the thoughts, it can be said that achieving a certain level of artistic and aesthetic development of a child largely depends on the pedagogical and general cultural factors in which he was born and lives. There is an opportunity to influence the artistic and aesthetic development of the child more early. First of all, this is related to the rapid development of the child's personality, taking into account his psychophysiological and age characteristics in the perception of information at different levels, and forming the ability to learn them in practice. Educational activities are not self-contained, they do not have an integrative description, by conducting integrated training in communicative, visual, cognitive, constructive areas, all types of children's activities and their integration are fully implemented. doesn't. Despite the above deficiency, the integration of the content of preschool education has a positive value in the development of preschool education in our republic.

We would like to make the following recommendations based on these points:

¹¹ Qodirov V. Creative And Rule-Based Games As A Factor In Developing Children's Ability To Think Independently. PSYCHOLOGY AND EDUCATION (2021) 58(2): 11501-11506.

¹² Юсов Б.П. Взаимосвязь культурогенных факторов в формировании современного художественного мышления учителя образовательной области «Искусство» [Текст] / Б. П. Юсов. – Москва: Компания Спутник+, 2004. – 83 с.

effective use of age-appropriate poems, stories, fairy tales, proverbs, etc., which serve to form moral and aesthetic qualities in children through play in the process of mastering speech, which goes parallel with mental development in preschool age;

role models of adults, especially parents and educators, in the acquisition of many ways of behavior and behavior by children in the process of communication;

the current program is an integrated activity that ensures that a 5-6-year-old child acquires the indicated abilities during the educational activity in the field of "Creativity" in the curriculum of the preschool education organization "First Step" organization of classes;

taking into account the integration of various types of children's activities when organizing the process of mastering current educational programs.

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